

Dynamic Wideband Channel Sounding in an Urban Macrocellular Scenario at 15 GHz

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Abstract—Fifth-generation cellular networks have become a part of infrastructure of modern society to support the effective and efficient information exchange. Despite significant advancements in mobile cellular technologies, the radio frequency range between 6 GHz and millimeter-wave 26 GHz, specifically around 15 GHz, remains underexplored in cellular mobile communications. This paper describes the implementation of a channel sounder based on a software defined radio and its application to dynamic field measurements to investigate the potential and challenges associated with mobile communications at 15 GHz carrier in non-line-of-sight (NLOS) radio channel conditions. The work provides initial insights into propagation losses in NLOS conditions in this frequency band due to foliage and urban structures. Our measurements revealed a 20 dB loss due to building corner shadowing, a 10–15 dB loss from foliage blockage, and an 8–15 dB penetration loss through building windows.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cellular wireless technologies, presently the fifth-generation (5G) being the most recent standard, become an essential part of our daily life. Continuous development of the cellular wireless technology for the next generation is pursued by industries and supported by governmental initiatives, leading to an innovative concept of integration of communications and computation [1] and a design methodology of end-to-end cellular system [2]. Among physical layer technical enablers of the innovative concept and systems, the use of intermediate radio frequency spectrum between the presently-used bands, i.e., between below-6 GHz and millimeter-wave 26 GHz, has recently gained significant interests. Specifically, the frequency band between 6 and 24 GHz, centered around 15 GHz, is of their interests, which is called the cellular frequency range three (FR3) in the industry [3].

Since the 15-GHz frequency band has not been used for cellular mobile communications so far, our knowledge of its potential to provide wide-area coverage is limited. It is possible to predict it through wave propagation theories for a simple radio communication scenario, e.g., where a mobile station is in line-of-sight (LOS) of a base station, but applicability of the theories to more complex communication scenarios, e.g., *radio communications behind multiple building corners or deep inside a building*, is still an open problem because rigorous theories of radio wave propagation are usually computationally prohibitive and hence it is not feasible to obtain accurate coverage estimation. Experimental evidence of radio coverage plays significant role here as it serves as a basis in developing sub-optimal but computationally less-demanding methods to estimate the radio coverage.

There has been many reports of radio channel characteristics around 15 GHz frequency bands in indoor scenarios [4]–[11] and references therein. Those covering mobile cellular sce-

narios are fewer. For example, outdoor ultrawideband channel sounding covering 3–18 GHz [12], [13] shed lights on the variation of wideband channel characteristics across carrier frequencies. At 15 GHz non-line-of-sight (NLOS) conditions, the pathloss exponent of up to 5 was observed and showed the greater exponent in urban macrocellular (UMa) settings than microcellular (UMi) base station locations. A UMi channel measurement in outdoor square at 10 GHz [14] showed a pathloss exponent of 1.6 and 2.1 in LOS and NLOS conditions. Outdoor UMa and UMi channel sounding [15] reveals that coverage beyond a blocking object such as building corners cause up to 20 dB losses, probably making it a challenge to realize NLOS coverage beyond 100 m link distance. From these measurements, parameters of the industrial standard channel model are derived in [16]. UMi measurements [17], [18] at 15 GHz showed that coverage at lightly shadowed areas is possible, and that objects on the street level, e.g., parking and running bans, trees and roadside signs, contributed to multipaths. Outdoor-to-indoor (O2I) channel sounding [19] and ray-based channel modeling at 14 GHz [20] shows that reflection, vegetation losses and penetration loss through building exterior walls affects the multipath propagation most. Pathloss and cluster characteristics are reported in [21], [22] for device-to-device street-level links.

The small amount of experimental evidence of outdoor mobile radio coverage at 15 GHz band, especially in *deep NLOS mobile locations*, is the knowledge gap we identified through the literature survey, that our work intends to contribute to. The present paper reports a wideband channel sounder consisting of a universal software defined radio peripherals (USRP) and frequency converters. It is based on our earlier work of dynamic wideband channel sounding below 6 GHz [23], with integration of frequency converters to support 15 GHz measurements, new antennas suitable for UMa and UMi scenarios, and a power amplifier for an enhanced dynamic range. A signal coverage map for a UMa base station site, measured using the channel sounder, is provided to imply feasibility of NLOS and O2I link connectivity.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II details the channel sounder implementation. Section III discusses delay synchronization stability and dynamic range. Initial observations of NLOS coverage in a UMa scenario, including outdoor-to-indoor conditions, are presented in Section IV. Section V concludes the paper.

II. CHANNEL SOUNDER

A. Waveform and Receiver Algorithm

The implemented channel sounder consists of two USRP devices for the transmitter (TX) and the receiver (RX) both

controlled through LabVIEW software. The TX USRP set to be at the mobile station (MS) is controlled by a laptop to enhance the MS mobility. An Echo Express SE I chassis which is a Thunderbolt to PCIe card expansion system interfaces the laptop-USRP communication link. A powerful embedded computer in an NI PXIe-1088 chassis controls the RX side. Both ends have a Low-Noise (LN) Rubidium clock, which will be described in Section III-A. The clocks supply a 10 MHz reference signal to the USRPs and the LO source devices for frequency and delay synchronization.

The waveform and receiver algorithms are implemented in a HOST controlling PC and in Field programmable gate arrays (FPGAs) of the USRPs. At the TX end, the HOST code generates an orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) waveform. OFDM was adopted for the purpose of using the same system for real-time demonstration of data transmission, e.g., [24], [25], in the future. It then forwards the waveform to the FPGA of the TX USRP which are programmed to continuously stream the provided waveform. The waveform consists of 1280 time-samples including a cyclic prefix (CP) of 256 samples. With the USRPs supporting up to a maximum instantaneous bandwidth (BW) of 160 MHz, using 1024 OFDM subcarriers gives a subcarrier spacing of 156.25 kHz. This leads to a symbol duration of 8 μ s and a channel impulse response (CIR) resolution of 6.25 ns. The subcarriers are modulated by quadrature phase shift keying.

TABLE I
IMPORTANT PARAMETERS OF CHANNEL SOUNDER

Parameter	Value
Center frequency	15.01 GHz
Bandwidth	160 MHz
Waveform modulation	OFDM
Number of sub-carriers	1024
Cyclic prefix length	256
Channel impulse response resolution	6.25 ns
Subcarrier spacing	156.25 kHz
Maximum resolvable Doppler shift	78.125 kHz
TX power: 3 dB back-off from OP1dB	23 dBm
Dynamic range	140 dB

At the RX end serving as a base station (BS), the waveform is sampled at an IQ sampling rate of 160 MS/s with a 32 bits per IQ sample precision. To avoid overflow in the FPGA buffers during samples transfer to the embedded computer, the waveform is averaged over 8 OFDM symbols, reducing the USRP-to-HOST data rate down to 20 MS/s. Hence, each recorded OFDM symbol corresponds to the duration of 8 OFDM symbols i.e., 64 μ s. The duration is sufficiently short for most time-varying channel sounding scenarios except for high-speed vehicular ones. For most scenarios, we can assume wide-sense stationarity of the measured channels. At the RX-control computer, the incoming waveform data is exported into binary data files for offline processing. The HOST code also processes some chunks of the sampled waveform in real time and plots the CIR which helps the sounder operators to get an instant look at the ongoing measurement.

B. Radio Frequency Parts

1) *Frequency Converters*: The USRPs used can provide an intermediate carrier frequency range of 10 MHz to 6 GHz.

Aiming at a target frequency of 15 GHz, the frequency synthesizer, up-converter, and down-converter described in table II have been employed. With the up and down converters supporting the RF range of 11–16 GHz, the frequency synthesizers are configured to output an LO signal of 14 GHz with the USRPs intermediate carrier frequency set to 1.01 GHz. The upper side band of the converted signal is at 15.01 GHz. Both the USRP and the frequency synthesizer receive the same 10 MHz reference signal delivered by the rubidium clock found at the corresponding end i.e., BS or MS.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of implemented sounder.

TABLE II
COMPONENTS USED IN CHANNEL SOUNDER

Component	Model
IF Devices	NI USRP-2954R
LO Source	NI QuickSyn Synthesizer FSW-0020
Up Converter	HMC709LC5
Down Converter	HMC113LP5E
Power Amplifier	ZVA-183G-S+
Reference Clocks	Jackson Labs LN Rubidium Clock
RX Controller	PXIe-1088 with PXIe-8374 card
TX Controller	Laptop connected to Echo Express SE I with PCIe-8374 card
RX Antenna	Wide-beamwidth Ku-band horn antenna
TX Antenna	Omnidirectional dipole antenna

2) *Antennas*: The BS antenna is a wide-beamwidth pyramidal horn antenna, designed and manufactured in-house from brass. The antenna has a realized gain of 8.7 dBi, with a beamwidth of 60° in the azimuth plane and 82° in the elevation plane. An omnidirectional dipole antenna was used as the MS antenna. The dipole has an azimuth plane out-of-roundness of 0.87 dB. The MS antenna was equipped with a 9 dB attenuator, resulting in a average realized gain of -8.5 dBi on azimuth plane. Figure 2 shows two orthogonal cuts, i.e. azimuth and elevation plane cuts, of radiation patterns of the antennas.

III. LABORATORY TESTS

A. Delay Synchronization

The phase and delay synchronization between the MS and BS is maintained through the LN Rubidium clocks integrated at both ends. Those clocks can provide a low noise 10 MHz reference signal. To ensure high stability, the clocks must be warmed up sufficiently. The warm-up phase can run in two different synchronization modes. The first mode would rely on the one pulse per second (1PPS) signal internally generated by the global navigation satellite system (GNSS) receiver in the clock. In this mode, the clocks must be connected to a

Fig. 2. Azimuth and elevation plane cuts of radiation patterns of (a) Wide-beamwidth Ku-band horn antenna and (b) omnidirectional dipole antenna at 15 GHz.

GPS antenna in a place with strong GPS signal strength. The other warm-up mode depends on an external 1PPS signal. The clocks are capable of generating a 1PPS signal upon power-on without the GNSS antenna being connected to the unit. This latter characteristic was employed in the adopted warm-up mode. One of the clocks was configured to generate a 1PPS signal, which was then fed into the 1PPS input of the other clock, establishing a master-slave configuration. The clocks must be warmed up for over 48 hours, after which the 1PPS cable was disconnected. Subsequently, the clocks operated in the holdover state, maintaining synchronization independently.

Knowing that the delay and phase synchronization will not be perfect, the clock drift effect has been investigated. In a cabled back-to-back (B2B) scenario, the peak of the CIR was monitored over time. Although the drift effect on the delay is continuous over time, the observed change of the peak delay in Fig. 4 appears discrete due to the finite resolution of the CIR measurements being 6.25 ns. Still, as the overall trend resembles a linear variation, linear interpolation is used to estimate the delay shift in each measurement route. During measurements, cabled B2B calibration was performed every 45 minutes. The difference in the absolute delay between two B2B calibration is so small that it can be linearly interpolated over time. A circular rotation to the CIR data over time is applied based on the corresponding shift at the route measurement time [26]. Beyond 9 hours, the delay drift deviates noticeably from the linear trend.

B. Dynamic Range

Over-the-air test measurements was performed using the sounder, where the MS followed a predefined route in a corridor. Obtained CIR included peaks whose delays correspond to those of a LOS path and a reflection from a nearby wall. The dynamic range was determined by observing the path gain at delays greater than $2 \mu\text{s}$ where no signal and hence only noise is received. The observed noise level seen in Fig. 3 lies below -140 dB path gain. With a few decibels of a margin from the noise average power, the dynamic range is 140 dB.

IV. TEST FIELD MEASUREMENTS

A. Setup

The field measurement took place on suburban Aalto University campus. The BS antenna mimicking the UMa scenario was installed on a building rooftop at 14 m from ground and

Fig. 3. CIR sample from test measurements where the noise level lies below a PG level of -140 dB.

Fig. 4. Laboratory measurement of the path delay change over time imposed by clocks drift in a cabled B2B scenario.

directed in two different sectors as shown in Figs. 5 and 6. The first illuminates part of a parking lot where building corners are found and some foliage obstruction. The second is directed towards the close building for an O2I study. The MS antenna is mounted on a cart at a height of 1.5 m. The sounder operator moves the cart along the planned routes while the received waveform data is recorded between the start and end of the routes. During the measurements, pedestrians and cars are occasionally moving at the parking lot but do not obstruct the LOS. Mild wind furthermore stirs leaves of birch trees, contributing to dynamics of the physical environment but their impact on channel observations are most likely minor.

B. Post Data Processing

The saved sampled waveform undergoes a preliminary processing to estimate CIR. The binary data is converted into complex IQ data. The complex waveform is then read starting at a sample instant subject to a shift by the phase drift of the

Fig. 5. Outdoor coverage map showing the link path gain in dB along the measurement routes.

Fig. 6. O2I coverage map showing the link path gain in dB along the measurement routes.

clocks described in Sec. III-A. B2B calibration is applied to the channel transfer function before further OFDM demodulation is performed. The channel transfer function matrix is denoted by $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$, where its entry of the n th row and m th column $\mathbf{H}(n, m)$ represents the transfer function at subcarrier n and the m th OFDM symbols recorded over a route. It is described as

$$\mathbf{H}(n, m) = \frac{\mathbf{H}_{\text{raw}}(n, m)}{\mathbf{H}_{\text{B2B}}(n)} \exp \left\{ -j2\pi \frac{(k_{\text{raw}} - k_{\text{B2B}} - s_{\text{drift}})n}{N} \right\},$$

where $\mathbf{H}_{\text{raw}}(n, m)$ and $\mathbf{H}_{\text{B2B}}(n, m)$ are the channel transfer functions of field and B2B calibration measurements respectively; k_{raw} and k_{B2B} are an instant in the waveform where an OFDM symbol starts in the field measurement and B2B calibration respectively calculated through the maximum likelihood estimator [27]; s_{drift} is the equivalent sample-instant shift due to the phase drift of the rubidium clocks calculated as in Sec. III-A; N is the number of frequency subcarriers and M is the total number of OFDM symbols recorded every $64 \mu\text{s}$ throughout a single MS route measurement.

A matrix representing a time-varying channel impulse response $\mathbf{H}_{\text{cir}} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$ is then computed by applying inverse fast Fourier transform to each column of \mathbf{H} . The coverage data, referred to as link path gain (PG) is calculated from \mathbf{H}_{cir} by adding up, for each channel instant, the multipath signals' path gains exceeding the assumed noise level i.e., -140 dB.

C. Results and Discussions

Figures 5 and 6 depict the coverage maps according to the measured MS routes.

1) *Outdoor Scenario*: The outdoor environment illustrated in Fig. 5 includes features critical for understanding wave propagation and assessing the feasibility of NLOS link connectivity. For example, Route 3 serves as a case study where the MS transitions from LOS visibility to NLOS conditions behind a building corner. Route 7 is entirely NLOS, beginning with foliage-induced shadowing and extending behind another building corner, culminating in a location where signal outage occurs. Routes 12, 13, and 14 are all in NLOS conditions due to foliage obstruction alone. From the coverage map observations, we can infer approximate values for signal attenuation due to building corners and foliage blockage. The estimated signal strength reduction is approximately 20 dB around corners and 10–15 dB due to foliage obstruction, as calculated by

$$PL_{\text{dB}} = FSPL_{\text{dB}} + L_{\text{foliage, dB}}, \quad (1)$$

where PL_{dB} is the path loss (PL) of a link, $FSPL_{\text{dB}}$ is the free space path loss (FSPL) over the direct-path distance separating the BS and MS, and $L_{\text{foliage, dB}}$ is the extra loss induced by the foliage here. The last term would include power loss due to scattering and penetration loss of the vegetation.

2) *O2I Scenario*: The O2I coverage map shows the viability of an O2I link with a glass penetration loss of 8–15 dB for an incidence angle on the glass around 15° where 0° represents a normal incidence. In addition, a deeper indoor route 6 still observes some signals possibly due to a reflection of the external-glass-penetrated signal on the internal glass wall 2 indicated in Fig. 6. The PG at an MS close to glass wall 2 is about 10 dB higher than that of PG of route 6, inferring a reflection loss on the glass wall 2 for an glazing incidence of around 70° where 0° represents a normal incidence.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented utilizing the USRP-based channel sounder for dynamic characterization of wave propagation in a UMa scenario covering NLOS conditions due to foliage and urban structures. It was found that some extent of coverage was possible for the concerned NLOS conditions. We observed a 20 dB extra loss when an MS is behind a building corner, a 10–15 dB loss due to foliage blockage, and an 8–15 dB penetration loss through building windows. In general, the losses due to blockage and penetration depends on sites, building and material types, suggesting much more measured evidence of them through extensive channel sounding in additional UMa and UMi scenarios. Future research expands these campaigns to additional sites. A systematic comparison of large-scale and small-scale channel characteristics with the 3GPP model is planned, along with a detailed investigation into foliage and building entry loss behavior in the 15 GHz band.

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